

Characterization and Statistical Analysis of Single Fiber Strength of Fibers at Various Processing Stages

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Introduction, motivation and objectives

Why characterize single fibre?!

- Fibre failure kinetics a key parameter for failure modelling in composites
- Composites are strongly overdesigned because of unreliability of the constituent properties such as fibres
- For critical applications such as pressure vessels, single fibre characterization becomes more critical
- Success of a stochastic model, depends on correctly capturing fibre strength statistics and failure kinetics

Objectives

- Addressing the challenges for automatic characterization of carbon and glass fibers in single fibre tensile tests (SFT)
- Finding answer to the question: if the tensile strengths and Weibull parameter of fibers are altered at several processing stages for Carbon T700S and E-CR Advantex Glass
- Understanding experimental uncertainties and ideal distribution for single fiber testing

Conventional single fibre testing

Automated single fibre testing

Observations, results and discussions

